

Learning dynamical systems from quantized observations: a Bayesian perspective

Dario Piga, Manas Mejari, and Marco Forgione

Abstract— Identification of dynamical systems from low-resolution quantized observations presents several challenges because of the limited amount of information available in the data and since proper algorithms have to be designed to handle the error due to quantization. In this paper, we consider identification of *Infinite Impulse Response* (IIR) models from quantized outputs. Algorithms both for maximum-likelihood estimation and Bayesian inference are developed. Finally, a particle-filter approach is presented for recursive reconstruction of the latent non-quantized outputs from past quantized observations.

Index Terms— System identification; Bayesian inference; maximum likelihood; quantized data.

I. INTRODUCTION

Although significant improvements in hardware speed, precision, and computational power have been seen in the last decades, only low-resolution quantized data are often available in some engineering applications. This is due to limitations in transmission networks or simply because cheap and low-resolution quantized sensors (e.g., binary-valued sensors) are often used in real-time applications. Because of the limited information contained in low-resolution data, identification of dynamical systems from quantized observations poses several challenges and has attracted the attention of many researchers [25]. Indeed, even in the case of simple *Linear Time-Invariant* (LTI) systems, conventional algorithms like least-squares may lead to poor estimates of the system parameters due to the bias introduced by the quantization noise [13]. In order to improve the parameter estimate, an approach based on *instrumental variables* and multi-step prediction is presented in [24], while in [1] quantization noise shaping techniques are developed to properly choose the quantization mechanism.

System identification from binary sensors is addressed in [15] for *Finite Impulse Response* (FIR) models under the (strong) assumption that that noise distribution is exactly known. Algorithms for identification of FIR models from binary input and output measurements have been recently presented in [16], [22]. Both of these contributions are based on the assumption that the (hidden) input is normally distributed. This assumption is relaxed in [9], [14], [26]. Two algorithms for recursive identification of *Infinite Impulse Response* (IIR)

models via binary sensors with adjustable threshold is addressed in [10].

Several contributions have been also proposed in the more general case of multi-level quantized data. Results on identification of FIR and IIR models are given in [5]–[7], [21] in the set-membership setting, where a bounded description of the quantization error is adopted. Contributions are also available in the stochastic framework. Maximum-likelihood estimation of *multi-input multi-output* FIR model parameters is addressed in [12]. This work is extended by the same authors in [11] for sparse identification of FIR models by formulating the estimation problem in a *Maximum-A-Posteriori* (MAP) framework. Generalized quantization schemes with noise-shaping filters are also used, and these filters, if properly designed, can improve the accuracy of the parameter estimates.

A. Paper contributions and related literature

This paper is focused on identification of IIR models from multi-level quantized data. A Bayesian framework is adopted and the following problems are addressed:

- maximum-likelihood and maximum-a-posteriori estimation of the IIR model parameters; initial conditions; and noise variance.
- approximation of the posterior distribution of the unknown parameters through Laplace’s method and *Markov Chain Monte Carlo* (MCMC);
- probabilistic inference of an output sequence given a new (not used for training) input sequence;
- filtering problem, which aims at iteratively reconstructing the non-quantized output from past observations of quantized outputs and a Bayesian estimate of the model. To this aim, a particle filter algorithm is constructed.

To position our work in the literature on system identification from quantized data, it is worth mentioning the contributions [4], [8], [23] which address identification of FIR systems from a Bayesian perspective. Specifically, the unknown impulse response is modelled as a realization of a Gaussian Process, with covariance matrix described by *stable spline kernels* [20]. Gibbs sampler is used in [4] to approximate the posterior distribution of the impulse response. This method requires sampling the unknown non-quantized output, and thus its computational burden increases fast with the size of the dataset. On the other hand, in our approach we only sample from the space of the IIR model parameters, initial conditions and noise variance. Thus, the dimension of the sampling space does not increase with the size of the dataset. In [8], an

This work was partially supported by the European H2020-CS2 project ADMITTED, Grant agreement no. GA832003.

The authors are with the IDSIA Dalle Molle Institute for Artificial Intelligence, USI-SUPSI, Via la Santa 1, 6962 Lugano, Switzerland. (e-mails: {name.surname}@supsi.ch). Corresponding author D. Piga.

expectation-maximization algorithm is proposed to compute the MAP estimate of the FIR model parameters. However, only single-point estimates are discussed, while our approach addresses complete approximation of the posterior distribution of the model parameters and of new output sequences. In [23], a variational approximation of the likelihood and of the posterior distribution of the impulse response is constructed and then used to find (an approximation of) the maximum-likelihood and maximum-a posteriori estimator. Like in [8], only a single-point estimate is computed. Maximum-likelihood estimation of ARMA models is considered in [17], where an online algorithm which asymptotically achieves the minimum parameter estimation error covariance is proposed. A frequentist approach is followed and a single-point estimate of the model parameters is provided.

B. Paper outline

The manuscript is organized as follows. The identification problem is formalized in Section II. Maximum-likelihood estimation is discussed in Section III. The Bayesian framework is introduced in Section IV, where algorithms for: MAP estimate; approximation of the posterior distributions of the unknown parameters; and system's output inference are presented. The filtering problem is discussed in Section V. The effectiveness of the approach is shown in Section VI through numerical examples. Detailed derivations of the main results of the paper are provided in the accompanying technical report [19].

C. Notation

All vectors are assumed to be column vectors, unless stated differently. A superscript \top denotes the transpose of a vector or a matrix and $|A|$ is the determinant of a square matrix A . The Dirac's delta function centred in a is denoted by $\delta_a(\cdot)$. The D -dimensional multivariate Normal distribution with mean $\mu \in \mathbb{R}^D$ and covariance matrix $\Sigma \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ is denoted as $\mathcal{N}(\mu, \Sigma)$, and $\mathcal{N}(x; \mu, \Sigma)$ is its probability density function.

II. PROBLEM SETTING

A. System description

Let us consider an LTI system \mathcal{S} described by

$$x(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i x(k-i) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} b_j u(k-j), \quad (1)$$

where $x(k)$ and $u(k)$ are the system's output and input, respectively, at time k ; n_a and n_b are fixed integers defining the order of the system; and $a_i \in \mathbb{R}$ (with $i = 1, \dots, n_a$) and $b_j \in \mathbb{R}$ (with $j = 1, \dots, n_b$) are unknown parameters to be estimated. To compact the notation, we collect the parameters a_i and b_i in the vector $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{n_\theta}$, with $n_\theta = n_a + n_b$ and $\theta = [a_1 \dots a_{n_a} \ b_1 \dots b_{n_b}]^\top$. The initial conditions of the output $x_0 = [x(-n_a + 1) \dots x(0)]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a}$ are unknown.

The output $x(k)$ is corrupted by an additive noise $e(k)$, i.e., $y(k) = x(k) + e(k)$, where $y(k)$ denotes the noisy output. The noise $e(k)$ is supposed to be generated by a white random process, and $e(k)$ is normally distributed with zero mean and unknown variance σ_e^2 , i.e., $e(k) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_e^2)$. Furthermore,

$e(k)$ is supposed to be statistically independent of the latent output $x(k)$ and of the system input $u(k)$. We assume that the (noisy) output $y(k)$ is not directly observed, but only a *quantized* measurement $v(k)$ of $y(k)$ is available, namely:

$$v(k) = Q(y(k)), \quad (2)$$

where $Q(\cdot)$ is the quantizing operator, defined by

$$Q(y) = v \quad \text{if } y \in (q_v, q_{v+1}], \quad (3)$$

where $v \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ (with K being the number of quantization intervals), and $(q_i, q_{i+1}]$ defines the range of the i -th quantization interval, which is assumed to be known. Note that q_1 and q_{K+1} can be equal to $-\infty$ and $+\infty$, respectively.

B. Addressed problems

Let \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{U} be the available datasets containing quantized output observations and inputs up to time N , respectively, namely $\mathcal{V} = \{v(k)\}_{k=1}^N$ and $\mathcal{U} = \{u(k)\}_{k=-n_b+1}^N$. The following learning problems will be addressed in the paper:

- *Maximum likelihood estimation* of the unknown model parameters θ , initial conditions x_0 , and noise standard deviation σ_e ;
- *Bayesian inference*, with: (i) maximum-a-posteriori estimate of θ , x_0 and σ_e ; (ii) approximation of the posterior distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$; (iii) inference of a new (not used for training) output sequence;
- *Filtering*, for recursive reconstruction of the output $x(k)$ given quantized output observations $v(k)$ up to time k .

III. MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION

A. Likelihood definition

Because of the conditional independence of the observed quantized outputs $v(k)$ given the latent output $x(k)$, the likelihood function of the parameters θ , the initial conditions x_0 and the noise standard deviation σ_e is given by

$$L(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e) = p(\mathcal{V} | \mathcal{U}; \theta, x_0, \sigma_e) \quad (4a)$$

$$= \prod_{k=1}^N p(v(k) | x(k), \sigma_e) = \prod_{k=1}^N p(Q(x(k) + e(k)) = v(k)) \quad (4b)$$

$$= \prod_{k=1}^N p(q_{v(k)} \leq x(k) + e(k) \leq q_{v(k)+1}) = \quad (4c)$$

$$= \prod_{k=1}^N \left(\Phi \left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1} - x(k)}{\sigma_e} \right) - \Phi \left(\frac{q_{v(k)} - x(k)}{\sigma_e} \right) \right), \quad (4d)$$

where Φ is the cumulative density function of the Normal distribution, i.e., $\Phi(x) = \int_{w=-\infty}^x \mathcal{N}(w; 0, 1) dw$.

B. Likelihood maximization

For maximum likelihood estimation, let us consider the *logarithm* of $L(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e) &= \log L(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e) = \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^N \log \left(\Phi \left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1} - x(k)}{\sigma_e} \right) - \Phi \left(\frac{q_{v(k)} - x(k)}{\sigma_e} \right) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Maximization of the log-likelihood $\mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e)$ is performed through a gradient-ascent approach, which requires to compute the gradients of $\mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e)$ (at each iteration of the gradient-ascent algorithm) w.r.t. θ , x_0 , and σ_e .

1) *Gradient with respect to the model parameters θ* : The gradient of the log-likelihood \mathcal{L} w.r.t. the model parameters θ can be derived by simple rules of calculus and noticing that $\frac{d\Phi(x)}{dx} = \mathcal{N}(x; 0, 1)$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right) - \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right)} \times \frac{1}{\sigma_e} \left(-\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial \theta}\right). \quad (6)$$

Note that evaluation of $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta}$ requires to compute $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial \theta}$ for all $k = 1, \dots, N$. Following the same approach commonly used in *prediction error methods* (PEM), the partial derivatives $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial a_i}$ (with $i = 1, \dots, n_a$) and $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial b_j}$ (with $j = 1, \dots, n_b$) can be computed by taking the derivative of left and right side of eq. (1) w.r.t. a_i and b_j , which yields

$$\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial a_i} = x(k-i) + \sum_{t=1}^{n_a} a_t \frac{\partial x(k-t)}{\partial a_i}, \quad (7a)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial b_j} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i \frac{\partial x(k-i)}{\partial b_j} + u(k-j). \quad (7b)$$

Thus, $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial a_i}$ and $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial b_j}$ can be computed by simulating the difference equation (7a) and (7b), respectively. Note that the term $x(k)$ appearing in (6) and (7a) has to be computed at each iteration of the gradient-ascent algorithm by simulating the dynamical model (1) using the current value of the model parameters θ and of the initial conditions x_0 .

2) *Gradient with respect to the initial conditions x_0* : The gradient of the log-likelihood \mathcal{L} w.r.t. x_0 is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_0} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{\mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right) - \mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right)}{\Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right)} \times \frac{1}{\sigma_e} \left(-\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial x_0}\right) \quad (8)$$

The gradient $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial x_0}$ appearing in (8) is derived by differentiation the left and right hand side of (1):

$$\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial x_0} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i \frac{\partial x(k-i)}{\partial x_0}. \quad (9)$$

Thus, $\frac{\partial x(k)}{\partial x_0}$ can be computed by simulating the autonomous dynamical system (9), with initial conditions

$$\frac{\partial x(1-j)}{\partial x_0} = \mathbf{e}_{n_a+1-j}, \quad j = 1, \dots, n_a \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{e}_j is the canonical vector, which has value zero for all elements except for index j which takes value 1. It is worth pointing out that (10) holds if we do not consider the inter-dependence within the elements of the initial conditions' vector x_0 .

3) *Derivative with respect to the noise standard deviation σ_e* : The partial derivative of the log-likelihood w.r.t. the noise standard deviation σ_e is given by:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \sigma_e} = \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{-\mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right) (q_{v(k)+1} - x(k))}{\sigma_e^2} - \frac{-\mathcal{N}\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}; 0, 1\right) (q_{v(k)} - x(k))}{\sigma_e^2} \right) \times \frac{1}{\Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)+1}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right) - \Phi\left(\frac{q_{v(k)}-x(k)}{\sigma_e}\right)}. \quad (11)$$

Note that the terms $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta}$ (eq. (6)), $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial x_0}$ (eq. (8)) and $\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \sigma_e}$ (eq. (11)) have several factors in common that can be evaluated only once at each iteration to reduce the computational burden of the gradient-ascent algorithm.

IV. BAYESIAN INFERENCE

In this section, we address the estimation of θ , x_0 and σ_e in a Bayesian setting, and thus we aim at computing the posterior probability distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \sigma_e | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. In order to simplify the derivations and to take into account the constraint $\sigma_e > 0$, the distribution of the noise $e(k)$ is parametrized in terms of the logarithm $\bar{\tau}$ of the noise precision, *i.e.*, $\bar{\tau} = \log \sigma_e^{-2}$. Thus, in the following, our distribution of interest is $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$.

As a prior distribution for θ , x_0 and $\bar{\tau}$, we use an isotropic Gaussian with zero mean and covariance matrix $\lambda^2 I$, *i.e.*,

$$p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}) = \mathcal{N}([\theta^\top \ x_0^\top \ \bar{\tau}]^\top; 0, \lambda^2 I) \quad (12)$$

where λ is a positive hyper-parameter and I is the identity matrix of size $n_\theta + n_a + 1$.

From Bayes' rule, the posterior probability distribution of the unknown parameters θ , x_0 and $\bar{\tau}$ is given by:

$$p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) = \frac{p(\mathcal{V} | \mathcal{U}, \theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}) p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})}{p(\mathcal{V} | \mathcal{U})}. \quad (13)$$

A. Maximum-a-posteriori estimation

We first focus on the computation of the *maximum-a-posteriori* (MAP) estimate of θ , x_0 and $\bar{\tau}$, which is by definition the mode of the posterior distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. This estimate is denoted as θ^{MAP} , x_0^{MAP} , $\bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}}$.

As in the case of maximum likelihood estimation, a gradient-ascent approach is used to maximize (w.r.t. θ , x_0 and $\bar{\tau}$) the logarithm of the posterior (13), which is given by:

$$\log p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) = \mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}) + \log p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}) - \log p(\mathcal{V} | \mathcal{U}).$$

Note that the term $\log p(\mathcal{V} | \mathcal{U})$ in the previous equation does not depend on θ , x_0 , $\bar{\tau}$ and thus it is ignored in the optimization. The gradient of the log-prior $\log p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ can be easily computed as $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ is Gaussian (eq. (12)). As for the derivative of the log-likelihood $\mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ w.r.t. $\bar{\tau}$, it can be easily computed from (11), and it is equal to

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \bar{\tau}} = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \sigma_e} \frac{\partial \sigma_e}{\partial \bar{\tau}} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \sigma_e} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\exp(\bar{\tau})}}. \quad (14)$$

B. Posterior approximation

In the following, we present two possible approximations for the whole posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$, which is in general a complex and intractable probability distribution.

The first approach is based on Laplace's method [3, Ch. 4.4] and leads to a Gaussian approximation of the intractable distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. The second approach is based on Monte Carlo sampling techniques and leads to a point-mass approximation of the same distribution.

1) *Version 1: Laplace approximation*: Laplace's method is used to approximate the posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ as a Gaussian distribution. To this aim, the following second-order Taylor expansion of the logarithm of the numerator in (13) centred around its peak $(\theta^{\text{MAP}}, x_0^{\text{MAP}}, \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}})$ is considered

$$\begin{aligned} & \log(p(\mathcal{V}|\mathcal{U}, \theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})) \approx \\ & \log\left(p(\mathcal{V}|\mathcal{U}, \theta^{\text{MAP}}, x_0^{\text{MAP}}, \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}})p(\theta^{\text{MAP}}, x_0^{\text{MAP}}, \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}})\right) + \\ & -\frac{1}{2}[(\theta - \theta^{\text{MAP}})^\top \quad (x_0 - x_0^{\text{MAP}})^\top \quad (\bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}})] \Lambda \begin{bmatrix} \theta - \theta^{\text{MAP}} \\ x_0 - x_0^{\text{MAP}} \\ \bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where Λ is the Hessian matrix of (minus) the log-posterior $-\log p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ evaluated at $\theta^{\text{MAP}}, x_0^{\text{MAP}}, \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}}$, whose entries contain the second derivatives of (minus) the log-likelihood $-\mathcal{L}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ and of (minus) the log-prior $-\log(p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}))$ w.r.t. θ , x_0 , and $\bar{\tau}$. Their analytical expressions are provided in [19, Appendix].

Laplace's approximation of the posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ is obtained by taking the exponent of the Taylor expansion in (15) and normalizing it. This leads to the Gaussian approximation

$$\begin{aligned} p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) & \approx p_{LAP}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) = \\ & = \frac{|\Lambda|^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(2\pi)^{\frac{n_\theta + n_a + 1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \theta - \theta^{\text{MAP}} \\ x_0 - x_0^{\text{MAP}} \\ \bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}} \end{bmatrix}^\top \Lambda \begin{bmatrix} \theta - \theta^{\text{MAP}} \\ x_0 - x_0^{\text{MAP}} \\ \bar{\tau} - \bar{\tau}^{\text{MAP}} \end{bmatrix}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

2) *Version 2: MCMC approximation*: In this paragraph, we discuss approximations of the entire posterior probability distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ using *Markov Chain Monte-Carlo* (MCMC) algorithms, which attempt to simulate draws from a complex distribution of interest [2].

The main idea behind application of MCMC to the considered inference problem consists in generating a sequence of H random samples $\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]$, $h = 1, 2, \dots, H$, from an irreducible and aperiodic Markov chain whose stationary distribution is the target posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. Once samples are generated, the posterior is approximated by the empirical point-mass distribution

$$p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) \approx \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \delta_{(\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h])}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}). \quad (17)$$

The *independent sampler*, an instance of the well-known Metropolis-Hastings MCMC method [2], is used to draw samples from $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$, as outlined in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 Approximation of the posterior distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ through independent sampler MCMC.

Inputs: initial samples $\theta[0], x_0[0], \bar{\tau}[0]$; proposal distribution $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$; data samples \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{U} .

- 1: **for** $h = 0, \dots, H - 1$ **do**
 - 2: draw candidate sample $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ from proposal $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$;
 - 3: **set** acceptance probability

$$\mathcal{A}(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*, \theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]) \leftarrow \min\left\{1, \frac{p(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})q(\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h])}{p(\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})q(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*)}\right\}; \quad (18)$$
 - 4: **accept** candidate $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ with probability $\mathcal{A}(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*, \theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h])$;
 - 5: **if** the $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ is accepted **then**
 - 6: $\theta[h + 1], x_0[h + 1], \bar{\tau}[h + 1] \leftarrow \theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$;
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: $\theta[h + 1], x_0[h + 1], \bar{\tau}[h + 1] \leftarrow \theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]$;
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **end for**
-

Output: Samples $\{\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]\}_{h=1}^H$.

The algorithm simulates a Markov Chain with stationary distribution $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$, and it requires to specify: an initial sample $\theta[0], x_0[0], \bar{\tau}[0]$; a proposal distribution $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$; the length H of the Markov Chain.

At each iteration h , a candidate sample $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ is drawn from the distribution $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ (Step 2) and accepted with probability $\mathcal{A}(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*, \theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h])$ (Steps 3 and 4). It is worth noticing that the acceptance probability $\mathcal{A}(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*, \theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h])$ (eq. (18)) depends on the ratio $\frac{p(\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})}{p(\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})}$ and thus its evaluation does not require to compute the normalization constant $p(\mathcal{V}|\mathcal{U})$ in (13). Furthermore, for numerical reasons, it is often more convenient to compute the logarithm of this ratio. If the candidate sample $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ is accepted, then $\theta[h + 1], x_0[h + 1], \bar{\tau}[h + 1]$ is set to $\theta^*, x_0^*, \bar{\tau}^*$ (Step 6), otherwise $\theta[h + 1], x_0[h + 1], \bar{\tau}[h + 1]$ is set to the previous sample $\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]$ (Step 8). The output is the sequence of samples $\{\theta[h], x_0[h], \bar{\tau}[h]\}_{h=1}^H$ generated during the execution of the algorithm.

It is well known that the choice of the proposal distribution $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau})$ is crucial in any Metropolis-Hastings MCMC algorithm to rapid convergence to the target distribution. The proposal density leading to fastest convergence is obviously $q(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}) = p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. Unfortunately, $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ cannot be directly sampled, as it represents itself the target distribution to be approximated. Based on the above considerations, a reasonable proposal distribution is the Laplace approximation $p_{LAP}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ derived in Section IV-B.1.

C. Inference of system's output sequence

In this section, we discuss the estimation of the system's output $x^*(k)$ given a new (not used for training) sequence of inputs $\mathcal{U}_{k-1}^* = \{u^*(t)\}_{t=-n_b+1}^{k-1}$ up to time $k - 1$. Formally, we would like to compute the probability distribution

$p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)$, which is factorized as

$$\begin{aligned} & p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*) \\ &= \int \underbrace{\left(\int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*, x_0^*) p(x_0^*) dx_0^* \right)}_{p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)} p(\theta|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $p(x_0^*)$ represents the prior distribution of the initial conditions $x_0^* = [x^*(0), \dots, x^*(-n_a + 1)]^\top$ of the new sequence, which is assumed to be Gaussian with mean \bar{x}_0^* and covariance matrix $\text{Cov}(x_0^*)$. Note that the integral $\int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*, x_0^*) p(x_0^*) dx_0^* = p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)$ represents the probability distribution of the output of the LTI system (1) for a given input sequence \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^* , given parameters θ and Gaussian-distributed initial conditions x_0^* . In order to compute this integral, it is convenient to split the system's response $x^*(k)$ into a *forced* response term $x_F^*(k)$ driven by the (deterministic) input \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^* and a *natural* response term $x_N^*(k)$ due to the (stochastic) initial condition x_0^* :

$$\begin{aligned} x_F^*(k) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i x_F^*(k-i) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_b} b_j u^*(k-j) \\ &\quad \text{with } x_F^*(k) = 0 \text{ for } k \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} x_N^*(k) &= \sum_{i=1}^{n_a} a_i x_N^*(k-i) \\ &\quad \text{with } x_N^*(-k) = \bar{x}_0^*[k+1] \text{ for } k \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (20b)$$

$$x^*(k) = x_F^*(k) + x_N^*(k). \quad (20c)$$

For a given value of θ , the forced response term $x_F^*(k)$ in (20a) is deterministic, since the input sequence \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^* is known. Conversely, the natural response term $x_N^*(k)$ in (20b) is stochastic since the initial condition x_0^* is a random variable. Specifically, $x_N^*(k)$ may be written as

$$x_N^*(k) = EA^k x_0^*, \quad (21)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ a_{n_a} & a_{n_a-1} & a_{n_a-2} & \dots & a_2 & a_1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad E = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

Therefore, the probability distribution of $x^*(k)$ given θ is:

$$\begin{aligned} & p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*) = \\ & \mathcal{N}\left(x^*(k); x_F^*(k; \theta) + EA^k \bar{x}_0^*, EA^k \text{Cov}(x_0^*) (A^k)^\top E^\top\right). \end{aligned}$$

Given the explicit expression of $p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)$, the integral $\int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*) p(\theta|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta$ in (19) is approximated via Monte-Carlo sampling, either generating samples $\{\theta[h]\}_{h=1}^H$ from the marginal (over x_0 and $\bar{\tau}$) of the Laplace approximation $p_{LAP}(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ (eq. (16)) or using the samples already drawn through the MCMC scheme (Algorithm 1). The final distribution $p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)$ is then approximated by

a mixture of Gaussian distributions, *i.e.*,

$$\begin{aligned} p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*) &= \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H p(x^*(k)|\theta[h], \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*) = \\ & \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \mathcal{N}\left(x^*(k); x_F^*(k; \theta[h]) + EA^k[h] \bar{x}_0^*, \right. \\ & \left. EA^k[h] \text{Cov}(x_0^*) (A^k[h])^\top E^\top\right), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

where $A^k[h]$ denotes the value of A^k computed for $\theta = \theta[h]$.

V. FILTERING

In this section, we consider the problem of iteratively reconstructing the non-quantized output $x^*(k)$ at time k given: (i) past estimate $x^*(k-1)$ at time $k-1$ inferred from new sequences (not used for training) of quantized outputs \mathcal{V}_{k-1}^* and inputs; (ii) new input $u^*(k)$ and quantized output $v^*(k)$; (iii) uncertain parameters θ and $\bar{\tau}$ described by the posterior distribution $p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$, obtained by marginalizing either the Laplace in (16) or the MCMC approximation in (17) w.r.t. x_0 .

Specifically, we aim at recursively approximating the probability distribution $p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ from $p(x^*(k-1)|\mathcal{V}_{k-1}^*, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$. In this work, we do not exploit the new sequences \mathcal{V}_k^* and \mathcal{U}_k^* to update the probability distribution of θ and $\bar{\tau}$. Formally, we approximate $p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ as:

$$\begin{aligned} & p(x^*(k)|\mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) \\ &= \int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \bar{\tau}, \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta d\bar{\tau} \\ &= \int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \bar{\tau}, \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta d\bar{\tau} \\ &\approx \int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \bar{\tau}, \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta d\bar{\tau}. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The above integral is then approximated through Monte-Carlo sampling as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int p(x^*(k)|\theta, \bar{\tau}, \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}) d\theta d\bar{\tau} \\ &\approx \frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H p(x^*(k)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

where $\theta[h]$, $\bar{\tau}[h]$ are either drawn from the Laplace approximation of $p(\theta, \bar{\tau}|\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ or already available from the MCMC approximation (17).

The probability distribution (25) is approximated using a bank of particle filters. To this aim, we represent the system (1) in the controllable canonical state-space form:

$$\tilde{x}(k) = A\tilde{x}(k-1) + Bu(k-1); \quad x(k) = C\tilde{x}(k). \quad (26)$$

with $B = [0 \ \dots \ 0 \ 1]^\top$, $C = [b_{n_b} \ \dots \ b_2 \ b_1]$, and A in (22).¹

Based on the above state-space representation, the evolutionary equation of $\tilde{x}^*(k)$ for a given model parameter $\theta[h]$

¹The considered controllable canonical state-space form holds for $n_a = n_b$.

and the related non-linear output equation are given by:

$$\tilde{x}^*(k) = A[h]\tilde{x}^*(k-1) + Bu^*(k) + \eta(k) \quad (27a)$$

$$v^*(k) = Q(C[h]\tilde{x}^*(k) + e^*(k)) \quad (27b)$$

where $A[h]$ and $C[h]$ are the matrices in (26) defined for the sample $\theta[h]$, and $\eta(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_a}$ is a fictitious white process noise (described by a probability distribution $p(\eta)$) which is introduced to take into account a possible model mismatch between (27a) and the underlying dynamics (26).

Using particle filter algorithms, the probability distribution $p(\tilde{x}^*(k)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*)$ in (25) is iteratively approximated with the empirical point-mass distributions

$$p(\tilde{x}^*(k)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) \approx \sum_{l=1}^{N_p} w_{h,l}(k) \delta_{\tilde{x}_{h,l}^*(k)}(\tilde{x}^*(k)), \quad (28)$$

based on $p(\tilde{x}^*(k-1)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_{k-1}^*, \mathcal{U}_{k-1}^*)$ and current values of $v^*(k)$ and $u^*(k)$. In (28), N_p is the number of particles; $\tilde{x}_{h,l}^*(k)$ is the position of the l -th particle at time k associated to the sample $\theta[h]$ and $\bar{\tau}[h]$; and $w_{h,l}$ are non-negative weights associated to the particle, with $\sum_{l=1}^{N_p} w_{h,l} = 1$. The distribution of interest $p(x^*(k)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*)$ can be easily obtained from (28) as

$$p(x^*(k)|\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, \mathcal{U}_k^*) \approx \sum_{l=1}^{N_p} w_{h,l}(k) \delta_{x_{h,l}^*(k)}(x^*(k)), \quad (29)$$

with $x_{h,l}^*(k) = C[h]\tilde{x}_{h,l}^*(k)$.

VI. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

The effectiveness of the proposed identification algorithm is demonstrated via a numerical example. Results can be replicated by running the MATLAB codes that can be downloaded at <http://dariopiga.com/Software/QuBay.rar>.

The data are generated by the system described as in (1) with model orders $n_a = 4$ and $n_b = 4$. The true parameters are $a = [0.3 \ 0.4 \ 0.5 \ 0.6]$ and $b = [0.8 \ 0.7 \ 0.2 \ 0.1]$. We consider a training data with $N = 2000$ samples, generated by exciting the system with a white input signal uniformly distributed in the interval $[-1 \ 1]$. The output is corrupted by a zero-mean Gaussian noise $e(k)$ with variance $\sigma_e^2 = 0.36$.

In order to assess the statistical properties of the proposed method, a Monte-Carlo simulation of 100 runs is performed. At each run, a new realization of input and noise process is generated. The average *Signal-to-Noise Ratio* (SNR) over 100 runs is 9.8 dB, where the SNR for a single Monte-Carlo run is defined as $\text{SNR} = 10 \log \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N x^2(k)}{\sum_{k=1}^N e^2(k)}$.

For each Monte-Carlo run, the MAP estimates of the parameters $\bar{\theta} = [\theta^\top \ x_0^\top \ \bar{\tau}^\top]^\top$ are computed using an isotropic Gaussian with $\lambda = 1$ (see eq. (12)) as a prior. In the gradient-ascent algorithm, the initial condition on each parameter value is chosen randomly from a uniform distribution in the interval $(0, 1)$. The algorithm is terminated either when the maximum number of iterations $h_{\max} = 350$ is reached or when the norm of the variation of the objective function between two consecutive iterations is smaller than 10^{-8} .

TABLE I: Monte-Carlo analysis with 100 runs: true vs estimated parameters for $K = 8$ level quantizer.

	True	ML estimate (mean \pm std)	MAP estimate (mean \pm std)
a_1	0.30	0.2998 \pm 0.0219	0.2941 \pm 0.0222
a_2	-0.40	-0.4037 \pm 0.0160	-0.4035 \pm 0.0152
a_3	0.50	0.4961 \pm 0.0130	0.4964 \pm 0.0121
a_4	-0.60	-0.5969 \pm 0.0193	-0.5959 \pm 0.0168
b_1	0.80	0.7990 \pm 0.0386	0.8001 \pm 0.0379
b_2	0.70	0.7075 \pm 0.0318	0.7112 \pm 0.0303
b_3	-0.20	-0.1976 \pm 0.0427	-0.1903 \pm 0.0416
b_4	0.1	0.1134 \pm 0.0460	0.1108 \pm 0.0438
σ_e	0.6	0.6008 \pm 0.0167	0.6296 \pm 0.0142

Fig. 1: Monte-Carlo analysis: boxplots of achieved BFR indices with ML and MAP estimates for data quantized with different quantization levels $K = 2, 4, 8$.

The ML and MAP estimates of the model parameters and noise standard deviation σ_e are reported in Table I, for data generated using $K = 8$ quantization intervals, uniformly spaced in the range $[q_1 \ q_{K+1}] = [-9 \ 7]$.

In order to assess the effect of the number of quantization intervals K , we compute the ML and MAP estimates for three different quantization levels $K = 2, 4, 8$. For the binary quantizer ($K = 2$), the threshold is set equal to 1. For quantizers with $K = 4$ and $K = 8$, the quantization levels are uniformly spaced in the range $[q_1 \ q_{K+1}] = [-9 \ 8]$. The identified models with ML and MAP estimates are used to reconstruct the outputs. The match between the true output and the one obtained by simulating the estimated model is quantified on a noise-free validation data of length $N_{\text{val}} = 1000$, in terms of the *Best Fit Rate* (BFR) index $\text{BFR} = \max \left\{ 1 - \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{val}}} (x(k) - \hat{x}(k))^2}{\sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{val}}} (x(k) - \bar{x})^2}}, 0 \right\} \times 100\%$, where $x(k)$ and $\hat{x}(k)$ are the (non-quantized) true and open-loop simulated model output at time k , respectively and \bar{x} is the sample mean of the output over the validation set. The box-plots of the obtained BFRs are shown in Fig. 1. As expected, the overall accuracy increases with the number of quantization intervals.

Next, we compute the ML and MAP estimates by changing the length N of the training data set for a binary quantizer $K = 2$. In Fig. 2 we report the norm of the parameter estimation error $\|\theta_o - \theta\|_2$ and the CPU time (on a commercial laptop), for different values of N . The accuracy of the estimated parameters increases with increase in data size N , at the cost of a *linear* increase in computation time.

Laplace approximation and MCMC

We now compute the approximation of the posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ using both Laplace's method and MCMC algorithm, as described in Section IV-B. The MAP estimates of Laplace's approximation are computed by running the gradient

(a) parameter estimation error vs data size.

(b) CPU time (s) vs data size.

Fig. 2: Performance of the ML and MAP estimates using binary quantizer $K = 2$ for different data sizes.

TABLE II: True vs estimated parameters computed via Laplace and MCMC approximation, with binary $K = 2$ quantized data, for a single realization of input and noise sequence.

	True	Laplace approx (mean \pm std)	MCMC estimate (mean \pm std)
a_1	0.30	0.3362 ± 0.0360	0.3125 ± 0.0362
a_2	-0.40	-0.3832 ± 0.0268	-0.4025 ± 0.0193
a_3	0.50	0.4923 ± 0.0239	0.4756 ± 0.0205
a_4	-0.60	-0.6198 ± 0.0236	-0.6129 ± 0.0247
b_1	0.80	0.8238 ± 0.0436	0.8129 ± 0.0437
b_2	0.70	0.6720 ± 0.0565	0.7005 ± 0.0543
b_3	-0.20	-0.2499 ± 0.0690	-0.2013 ± 0.0589
b_4	0.1	0.1062 ± 0.0691	0.1508 ± 0.0600
$\bar{\tau}$	1.02	1.0148 ± 0.0522	1.0276 ± 0.0808

TABLE III: Monte-Carlo analysis: mean and std deviation of the mean of the parameters' estimates over 100 Monte-Carlo runs computed via Laplace and MCMC approximations.

	True	Laplace approx (mean \pm std)	MCMC estimate (mean \pm std)
a_1	0.30	0.2967 ± 0.0366	0.2914 ± 0.0490
a_2	-0.40	-0.4009 ± 0.0264	-0.4022 ± 0.0336
a_3	0.50	0.4991 ± 0.0265	0.4966 ± 0.0324
a_4	-0.60	-0.5988 ± 0.0232	-0.5939 ± 0.0260
b_1	0.80	0.8013 ± 0.0477	0.8000 ± 0.0500
b_2	0.70	0.7044 ± 0.0538	0.7077 ± 0.0676
b_3	-0.20	-0.1944 ± 0.0588	-0.1910 ± 0.0825
b_4	0.1	0.1046 ± 0.0683	0.1102 ± 0.0787
$\bar{\tau}$	1.02	0.9724 ± 0.0748	0.9837 ± 0.0915

ascent algorithm for $h_{\max} = 1000$ iterations. The mean and the standard deviation of Laplace's approximation are reported in Table II. In order to approximate the posterior $p(\theta, x_0, \bar{\tau} | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ via MCMC, Algorithm 1 is run for $M = 5000$ iterations. The estimated mean along with estimated standard deviations of the parameters are reported in Table II. Moreover, the mean and standard deviations of the mean of the estimates obtained via Laplace and MCMC approximation over 100 Monte-Carlo runs are reported in Table III.

The performance of the Laplace and MCMC approximations is further assessed for data generated with different quantization levels $K = 2, 4, 8$. Fig. 3 shows the estimate of the parameter a_1 along with its 3-standard deviation intervals computed from the Hessian Λ of Laplace approximation and through the MCMC samples.

Inference

Based on the samples generated by the MCMC algorithm, we infer the output $x^*(k)$ for a new sequence of inputs U_{k-1}^* as detailed in Section IV-C. To this end, we consider a new white input sequence of length 1000 samples generated from

Fig. 3: Laplace and MCMC approximation: (mean \pm 3std) of the estimated parameter a_1 for different quantization levels $K = 2, 4, 8$. True values are marked with red color.

Fig. 4: Inference: True output $x^*(k)$; expected value of the output $\mu_{x^*(k)}$ (dashed black); confidence intervals $\mu_{x^*(k)} \pm 3\sigma_{x^*(k)}$ (shaded grey region), computed with $H = 4000$ MCMC samples. Left panel: $K = 2$ quantization levels. Right panel: $K = 8$ quantization levels.

a uniform distribution in the interval $[-1, 1]$, which is not used for training. The distribution of the inferred output $x^*(k)$ sequence is computed according to eq. (23), by choosing as a prior distribution of the initial states x_0^* an isotropic zero-mean Gaussian with covariance matrix $(0.01)I_{n_a}$. The mean $\mu_{x^*(k)}$ and the uncertainty interval corresponding to $3\sigma_{x^*(k)}$ of the inferred output distribution $p(x^*(k) | \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U}, U_{k-1}^*)$ are plotted in Fig. 4, for $K = 2$ and $K = 8$ quantization intervals. For a better visualization, only a subset of output sequence is plotted.

Filtering

We now compute the distribution $p(x^*(k) | \mathcal{V}_k^*, U_k^*, \mathcal{V}, \mathcal{U})$ (given in (25)) of the latent output at time k given past observations, as described in Section V. To this end, we first compute the conditional distribution $p(\tilde{x}^*(k) | \theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, U_k^*)$ given in (29) for each of the MCMC samples $\{\theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h]\}_{h=1}^H$.

A dataset with 2000 samples is processed sequentially, simulating a scenario where samples are acquired and processed in real time. At each time k , the posterior $p(\tilde{x}^*(k) | \theta[h], \bar{\tau}[h], \mathcal{V}_k^*, U_k^*)$ is updated using a particle filter algorithm with $N_p = 100$ particles. Initial conditions $\{\tilde{x}_i^*(0)\}_{i=1}^{N_p}$ of the particles are sampled from a Gaussian prior distribution $p(\tilde{x}^*(0))$ with zero-mean and covariance $0.01I_{n_a}$. At each successive time steps, the particles $\{\tilde{x}_i^*(k)\}_{i=1}^{N_p}$ are sampled according to the evolutionary equation (27a), with a zero-mean isotropic Gaussian $p(\eta) = \mathcal{N}(\eta; 0, \sigma_\eta^2 I)$ (with $\sigma_\eta^2 = (0.05)^2$) describing the process noise η .

Analysis for multiple data-generating systems

Finally, we consider 50 different randomly-generated 4-th order stable systems. Quantized measurements with three different quantization intervals $K = 2, 4, 8$ are gathered, with training and validation data of lengths 2000 and 1000 samples, respectively. The quantization intervals are spaced uniformly

Fig. 5: Particle filtering: true output $x^*(k)$; expected value of the output $\mu_{x^*(k)}$ (dashed black); confidence intervals $\mu_{x^*(k)} \pm 3\sigma_{x^*(k)}$ (shaded gray region), computed with $H = 4000$ MCMC samples and $K = 2$ quantization levels.

Fig. 6: Boxplots of BFRs achieved by ML (light) and MAP (dark) estimates for 50 different data-generating systems.

between minimum and maximum value of the system output. The training output is corrupted by a Gaussian noise leading to an average SNR of 10 dB.

For MAP estimates, an isotropic Gaussian prior with $\lambda = 1$ in (12) is chosen. For each system, the gradient-ascent algorithm is run for 500 iterations, with initial condition of each parameter chosen randomly from a uniform distribution in the interval $(0, 0.1)$. The box-plots of the achieved BFR index with three quantization levels $K = 2, 4, 8$ are plotted in Fig. 6, which shows that the output is accurately reconstructed with quantized data for a majority of the 50 systems.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

A Bayesian framework for transfer function estimation of linear dynamical systems from quantized output observations is discussed in the paper. The gradient and the Hessian of the (log)-likelihood function w.r.t. the system parameters, initial conditions and noise standard deviation are computed and used: (i) for maximum likelihood and maximum-a-posteriori estimation; (ii) to approximate the posterior distribution of the unknown variables through Laplace's method or Markov-Chain Monte-Carlo. Predictive inference is also addressed. Finally, particle filters are used to recursively reconstruct a latent (non-quantized) output from past (quantized) observations. This is useful in control design, where hidden non-quantized outputs can be used to assess closed-loop performance and to make prediction of the next output sequence.

Extension to the more general case of identification of switched Box-Jenkins model structures is currently under investigation. This requires to combine the approach discussed in this paper with the algorithm in [18]. Experiment design and optimal choice of the quantization levels for minimization of model uncertainty are also topics to be addressed to extend and improve the presented results.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. C. Agüero, G. C. Goodwin, and J. I. Yuz. System identification using quantized data. In *46th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, pages 4263–4268, New Orleans, LA, USA, 2007.
- [2] C. Andrieu, N. De Freitas, A. Doucet, and M. I. Jordan. An introduction to MCMC for machine learning. *Machine learning*, 50(1-2):5–43, 2003.
- [3] C. M. Bishop. *Pattern recognition and machine learning*. Springer, 2006.
- [4] G. Bottegal, H. Hjalmarsson, and G. Pillonetto. A new kernel-based approach to system identification with quantized output data. *Automatica*, 85:145 – 152, 2017.
- [5] M. Casini, A. Garulli, and A. Vicino. Bounding nonconvex feasible sets in set membership identification: OE and ARX models with quantized information. In *16th IFAC Symposium on System Identification*, pages 1191 – 1196, Brussels, Belgium, 2012.
- [6] M. Casini, A. Garulli, and A. Vicino. Input design in worst-case system identification with quantized measurements. *Automatica*, 48(12):2997 – 3007, 2012.
- [7] V. Cerone, D. Piga, and D. Regruto. Fixed-order FIR approximation of linear systems from quantized input and output data. *Systems and Control Letters*, 62(12):1136 – 1142, 2013.
- [8] T. Chen, Y. Zhao, and L. Ljung. Impulse response estimation with binary measurements: A regularized FIR model approach. In *16th IFAC Symp. on System Identification*, pages 113–118, Brussels, Belgium, 2012.
- [9] E. Colinet and J. Juillard. A weighted least-squares approach to parameter estimation problems based on binary measurements. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 55(1):148–152, 2009.
- [10] B. Csáji and E. Weyer. Recursive estimation of ARX systems using binary sensors with adjustable thresholds. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 45(16):1185–1190, 2012.
- [11] B. I. Godoy, J. C. Agüero, R. Carvajal, G. C. Goodwin, and J. I. Yuz. Identification of sparse FIR systems using a general quantisation scheme. *International Journal of Control*, 87(4):874–886, 2014.
- [12] B. I. Godoy, G. C. Goodwin, J. C. Agüero, D. Marelli, and T. Wigren. On identification of FIR systems having quantized output data. *Automatica*, 47(9):1905 – 1915, 2011.
- [13] F. Gustafsson and R. Karlsson. Statistical results for system identification based on quantized observations. *Automatica*, 45:2794–2801, 12 2009.
- [14] S. Kan, G. Yin, and L. Y. Wang. Parameter estimation in systems with binary-valued observations and structural uncertainties. *International Journal of Control*, 87(5):1061–1075, 2014.
- [15] L. Y. Wang, J.F. Zhang, and G. G. Yin. System identification using binary sensors. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 48(11):1892–1907, 2003.
- [16] A. S. Leong, E. Weyer, and G. N. Nair. Identification of FIR systems with binary input and output observations. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 66(3):1190–1198, 2021.
- [17] D. Marelli, K. You, and M. Fu. Identification of ARMA models using intermittent and quantized output observations. *Automatica*, 49(2):360 – 369, 2013.
- [18] D. Piga, V. Breschi, and A. Bemporad. Estimation of jump Box-Jenkins models. *Automatica*, 120:109126, 2020.
- [19] D. Piga, M. Mejeri, and M. Forgiione. Learning dynamical systems from quantized observations: a Bayesian perspective. Technical report, 2021. <https://www.dariopiga.com/TR/TR-IDSIA-21-04.pdf>.
- [20] G. Pillonetto and G. De Nicolao. A new kernel-based approach for linear system identification. *Automatica*, 46(1):81 – 93, 2010.
- [21] M. Pouliquen, E. Pigeon, O. Gehan, and A. Goudjil. Identification using binary measurements for IIR systems. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 65(2):786–793, 2019.
- [22] M. Pouliquen, E. Pigeon, O. Gehan, A. Goudjil, and R. Auber. Impulse response identification from input/output binary measurements. *Automatica*, 123, 2021.
- [23] R. S. Risuleo, G. Bottegal, and H. Hjalmarsson. Identification of linear models from quantized data: A midpoint-projection approach. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, 65(7):2801–2813, 2020.
- [24] H. Suzuki and T. Sugie. System identification based on quantized i/o data corrupted with noises and its performance improvement. In *Proceedings of the 45th IEEE Conference on Decision and Control*, pages 3684–3689, San Diego, CA, USA, 2006.
- [25] L. Y. Wang, G. G. Yin, J. F. Zhang, and Y. Zhao. *System identification with quantized observations*. 2010.
- [26] L. Y. Wang, G. G. Yin, and J.F. Zhang. Joint identification of plant rational models and noise distribution functions using binary-valued observations. *Automatica*, 42(4):535 – 547, 2006.